

Selecting candidate articles for replication: the NanoBubbles replication initiative corpus creation

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The NanoBubbles' replication initiative focuses on articles that use nanoparticles for intracellular sensing of cytosolic targets. Therefore, a first task is to create a list of articles that are in scope. However, this task presents several challenges. A simple bibliographic search would yield articles corresponding to the detection of nanoparticles in cells (instead of the use of nanoparticles for detecting a target in the cells). An example of such a false positive is this article entitled "Nanohybrids via a polycation-based nanoemulsion method for dual-mode detection of human mesenchymal stem cells". We also considered articles that use nanoparticles in solar cells and biofilms as false positives since we are not interested by them.

After an exploratory phase, the following query was designed as an attempt to limit false positives while not restricting the search and missing relevant articles when searching in Web of Science:

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((((ALL=(gold nano* OR Au-NP* OR silver nano* OR Ag-NP* OR carbon dots OR c-dots)) AND ALL=(cell* OR intracellular)) AND ALL=(sensing OR detection OR diagnostic OR imaging OR recognition OR tracking OR monitoring OR biosensing OR bioimaging OR sensor OR probing)) NOT ALL=(biofilm*)) NOT ALL=(solar)) AND DT=(Article)
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All= search is carried out in all fields; OR=results containing any of the terms; AND= results containing all of the terms; NOT= Excludes results containing the terms; DT=document type; *= represents more letters

Briefly, in the above query:

1. 'articles' were selected as the type of document, since the NanoBubbles' replication initiative is interested in experimental studies and not other types of documents such as book chapters or proceeding papers.
2. As a way of limiting the number of false positives, the type of nanoparticles were specified as gold nanoparticles, silver nanoparticles, or carbon quantum dots. These three types of nanoparticles were found to be the most common types of nanoparticles amongst the relevant articles during the exploratory phase.
3. The articles selected were based on the topic they investigate. This we did by searching for articles that mentioned words that either explicitly captured or implied that the sensing was carried out inside cells i.e. 'intracellular' *and* either explicitly captured or implied that these nanoproboscopes were used to detect molecules.
4. To exclude some false positive articles in the corpus such as articles investigating the use of nanoproboscopes in biofilms, an example of which is "Imaging of intracellular behavior of polymeric nanoparticles in Staphylococcus epidermidis biofilms by slit-scanning confocal Raman microscopy and scanning electron microscopy with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy", we used the "NOT" feature on selected keywords such as "biofilm in this case.

This query run on Web of Science on March 20, 2023 gave 25,620 results. After removal of (at the time of search) recently published articles, i.e. published in the years 2022 and 2023, the final list consisted of 22,842 articles.

The citation counts were used to select what are likely to be the most influential articles. More precisely, the citation reports from this query were retrieved from Web of Science and categorized based on the years of publication (category A: 2021-2019; category B: 2018-2015; category C: 2014-1987). They were ranked (in each category) by decreasing 'average citation per year'. To further limit the size of the corpus, a lower cutoff value of 14 was set based on analysis done in the exploratory phase. This led to 258, 538, and 575 articles in category A, B and C respectively.

Next, researchers from the NanoBubbles' replication initiative manually went through the list of titles to remove any false positives such as articles entitled "Carbon Dots for Optical imaging *in vivo*", or "Thermo-plasmonics: using metallic nanostructures as nano-sources of heat". Furthermore, since the NanoBubbles' replication initiative is concerned with articles that claim the uptake of the nanoparticles by endocytosis rather than nanoparticles that are microinjected or transfected, researchers from the NanoBubbles' replication initiative looked into the article (not just the titles) to decide whether to include or not in the final list of potential candidates for replication.

Finally, this process yielded a list of 78 relevant articles (Table 1). Given the limited time-frame and financial resources, the list was narrowed down to a list of 8 articles (Table 2) based on additional criteria including:

1-Feasibility of the study

2-No more than one article per research team

3-Number of publications per journal in the list of 78 articles. For this, the journals were ranked based on how many times they appear in the list of 78 articles. Then, the top 4 journals that appear most were selected. Next, 2 articles from each of the 4 journals were added to the final list of 8 articles.

If the article that was in our selection was not feasible or there was a common author with another selected the next one that was published in the same journal was selected from the list of 78 articles.

Table 1: Initial list of 78 articles selected for the NanoBubbles' replication initiative

Publication Year	DOI	Total Citations	Average citations per year
2019	10.1016/j.jcis.2018.12.047	314	62.8
2017	10.1021/acsami.6b15746	360	51.43
2017	10.1016/j.snb.2016.10.068	312	44.57
2016	10.1021/jacs.5b10309	344	43
2014	10.1021/ac502446m	400	40
2012	10.1002/adma.201202599	458	38.17
2012	10.1002/anie.201109089	450	37.5
2013	10.1039/c2cc37329g	399	36.27
2016	10.1021/acs.analchem.5b04193	285	35.63
2017	10.1002/anie.201704147	248	35.43
2018	10.1021/acsami.7b16991	209	34.83
2014	10.1039/c3nr06353d	335	33.5
2007	10.1021/ja0776529	561	33
2017	10.1016/j.snb.2016.11.109	225	32.14
2017	10.1021/acsami.6b13954	221	31.57
2018	10.1016/j.carbon.2018.02.063	189	31.5
2017	10.1021/jacs.7b03617	220	31.43
2016	10.1021/acsami.6b01325	248	31
2012	10.1002/anie.201202533	372	31
2015	10.1016/j.bios.2015.06.050	271	30.11
2017	10.1002/adma.201606086	208	29.71
2020	10.1021/acsnano.0c05541	118	29.5
2013	10.1002/anie.201306366	314	28.55
2013	10.1021/ja400150v	309	28.09
2017	10.1021/acsnano.6b06670	195	27.86
2016	10.1002/anie.201509726	218	27.25
2017	10.1021/acssuschemeng.6b01893	190	27.14
2015	10.1021/jacs.5b04007	244	27.11
2016	10.1021/acs.analchem.6b01932	216	27
2015	10.1016/j.aca.2014.12.045	240	26.67
2017	10.1021/acs.analchem.7b04211	186	26.57
2017	10.1016/j.msec.2017.03.178	180	25.71
2014	10.1021/ac404236y	249	24.9
2016	10.1021/acsami.6b05465	188	23.5
2014	10.1016/j.snb.2013.11.041	234	23.4
2012	10.1002/anie.201203767	278	23.17
2015	10.1021/acsnano.5b02807	208	23.11
2013	10.1021/ja4035939	253	23
2016	10.1016/j.snb.2015.10.046	181	22.63

2011	10.1002/anie.201101351	280	21.54
2019	10.1002/anie.201903005	106	21.2
2016	10.1016/j.snb.2015.09.081	167	20.88
2019	10.1021/acsami.9b01319	104	20.8
2009	10.1021/nl901517b	312	20.8
2017	10.1002/anie.201701325	139	19.86
2015	10.1021/jacs.5b01457	177	19.67
2015	10.1016/j.aca.2015.09.050	176	19.56
2014	10.1039/c4ra10601f	195	19.5
2012	10.1021/ac202648w	233	19.42
2016	10.1021/acsami.5b11317	153	19.13
2014	10.1039/c4nr03213f	189	18.9
2017	10.1016/j.bios.2017.05.035	132	18.86
2019	10.1016/j.synthmet.2019.116183	94	18.8
2020	10.1021/acsami.0c00283	74	18.5
2014	10.1021/ac403810g	185	18.5
2016	10.1016/j.bios.2016.04.066	145	18.13
2020	10.1021/acs.analchem.0c01592	72	18
2012	10.1039/c2cc31000g	213	17.75
2017	10.1039/c7nr03658b	124	17.71
2014	10.1021/ac501499y	177	17.7
2011	10.1039/c0an00424c	229	17.62
2019	10.1007/s00604-018-3221-8	88	17.6
2014	10.1002/sml.201401658	176	17.6
2014	10.1021/ja5042995	175	17.5
2019	10.1021/acs.analchem.9b03272	87	17.4
2021	10.1002/anie.202012801	51	17
2016	10.1039/c6ra01669c	136	17
2017	10.1021/acs.analchem.7b01632	119	17
2017	10.1021/acs.analchem.6b04943	117	16.71
2012	10.1039/c2nr30219e	197	16.42
2017	10.1021/acs.analchem.7b00174	114	16.29
2019	10.1021/acsami.9b13737	81	16.2
2017	10.1021/acssuschemeng.7b00393	113	16.14
2015	10.1021/acsami.5b06523	145	16.11
2016	10.1016/j.snb.2016.06.126	127	15.88
2018	10.1016/j.aca.2018.06.051	95	15.83
2017	10.1021/acs.analchem.7b00697	110	15.71
2018	10.1002/anie.201805640	94	15.67

Table 2: Final list of 8 articles selected for the NanoBubbles' replication initiative

Publication Year	DOI	Total Citations	Average citations per year
2016	10.1021/jacs.5b10309	344	43
2012	10.1002/anie.201109089	450	37.5
2017	10.1002/anie.201704147	248	35.43
2007	10.1021/ja0776529	561	33
2017	10.1021/acsami.6b15746	360	51.43
2018	10.1021/acsami.7b16991	209	34.83
2014	10.1021/ac502446m	400	40
2014	10.1021/ac404236y	249	24.9

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